

Towards a Sustainable Liberia National Soil Information System (LiNSIS) The Regional Hub for Fertilizer and Soil Health for West Africa and the Sahel

5th -7th August 2025, Monrovia, Liberia

Workshop report

Table of Content

Table of Content	2
List of Abbreviation	3
Executive Summary	4
Acknowledgments	5
Introduction	6
Workshop Day 1:	7
Session 1 – Benefits of using the SIS framework	7
Session 2 – Current state of LibSIS and Live demo	7
Session 3 – Ideal System Design	8
Session 4 – SIS stakeholder map and requirements	9
Session 5 – Data requirements	11
Workshop Day 2:	14
Session 1- Future of the SIS	14
Session 2- Long term sustainability	15
Session 3- Partnership model	17
Session 4- Next steps	19
Annex 2: Flipcharts from different groups	24
Annex 3: List of Participants	29

List of Abbreviation

MoA	Ministry of Agriculture
CARI	Central Agricultural Research Institute
SIS	Soil Information System
ISRIC	International Soil Reference and Information Centre
CABI	Centre for Agriculture and Bioscience International
IITA	International Institute of Tropical Agriculture
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
DST	Decision Support Tool
GIS	Geographic Information System
UL	University of Liberia
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
EU	European Union
LiNSIS	Liberia National Soil Information System
LiNSIC	Liberia National Soil Information Centre
WB	World Bank
LLA	Land Authority
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
FDA	Forest Development Agency
AfDB	African Development Bank
IFAD	International Fund for Agricultural Development

Executive Summary

This SIS development report outlines the strategic steps for building and strengthening Liberia's Soil Information System (LiNSIS) to enhance agricultural productivity, soil health, and informed decision-making for sustainable soil management. It builds on insights from the "Liberia Soil Information System Development Workshop" held in August 2025 in Monrovia, Liberia, hosted by Regional Hub for Fertilizer and Soil Health for West Africa and the Sahel, IITA Liberia, MoA, CARI, UL, and ISRIC-World Soil Information in close collaboration with the EU funded Soils4Liberia project. Participants from various sectors addressed common data and capacity challenges and discussed long-term financial sustainability options for LiNSIS.

The workshop reviewed seven components of the SIS framework, crucial for LiNSIS's success: 1) envisioning the SIS, 2) enabling environment, 3) needs assessment, 4) SIS ideal system design, 5) partnership development and sustainability plan, 6) data strategy, and 7) organizational and financial sustainability plan. The roadmap includes an overview of each component, addressing available information, gaps, and recommendations, which are optional for the LiNSIS project team to consider.

The key potential next steps for CARI-MoA, UL and IITA to consider include:

- Organise a formal inception meeting (online) in August for Soils4Liberia project funded by EU. This can be done by IITA (The lead of Soils4Liberia project) to key partners.
- Organise a meeting for technical discussion and consultations on sampling design in August or September.
- Launch/Kick off Soils4Liberia project in October.
- Establishing a steering committee, and scientific and technical advisory group by October 2025 alone with project kick-off.
- Develop protocol, training & capacity building for CARI-MoA and UL team members.
- Upgrade of the soil lab at UL should be completed between September 2025 and January 2026.
- Field sampling design, lab analysis, lab quality control, and system design – technical architecture will be carried on 2026.
- Set up a financial sustainability plan, incorporating input from all relevant partners.
- Organize a validation workshop with broad stakeholder participation, once the design and work plans are in place and next steps are agreed upon.

The Soils4Liberia intend to establish the Liberia National Soil Information Centre (LiNSIC) for the LiNSIS strengthening process. A new team will be set up in this centre in collaboration MoA, CAR, and UL, and they will be responsible for setting strategic direction, overseeing system integrity, ensuring stakeholder coordination, guiding technical upgrades, monitoring compliance with data governance and quality standards, and, be the long term technical body responsible for LiNSIS.

Acknowledgments

CARI, MoA, UL, ISRIC-World Soil Information, Regional Hub for Fertilizer and Soil Health for West Africa and the Sahel, and IITA would like to thank workshop participants for their contributions that have led to the development of this roadmap. With special thanks to Regional Hub for Fertilizer and Soil Health for West Africa and the Sahel, and IITA for their support in organizing the workshop, and to CABI for their input and review.

More information, supporting resources and useful tools for each of the components are available in the online SIS framework, hosted on ISRIC's Resource Library and created by CABI and ISRIC – World Soil Information (<https://resources.isric.org/sis-framework/>).

If there are any questions or aspects of the roadmap that require further support or input from ISRIC, kindly contact chrow.khurshid@isric.org or thaisa.vanderwoude@isric.org

Introduction

A Soil Information System (SIS) is not just a digital platform but a collaborative tool that engages stakeholders, from government agencies to farmers, to improve data access, soil health management, and informed decision-making in Liberia's agriculture sector. Understanding how these people and institutions should work together, and aligning on who is responsible for what, is a critical step to ensuring the progress of the SIS. There are three levels to consider: the individual (suitable skills, knowledge, competencies, and attitudes), the organizational (efficient structures, processes, and procedures), and the governmental level (establishment of adequate institutions, laws, and regulations).

[CAB-International](#) and [ISRIC – World Soil Information](#), supported by the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, has created a framework for SIS development, assessing these levels at the start of a SIS intervention. The [SIS Framework](#) helps to identify activities needed to fulfil the SIS objectives, deciding also on the sequence in which these activities are best performed, who is going to do them, and identifying potential risks, with each specifically tailored to the country context. The SIS framework was the base for the LiNSIS development workshop which was held in August 2025 in Monrovia, Liberia.

The objectives of the LiNSIS development workshop were:

- Understanding the needs for a SIS
- Lessons learned from the FAO pilot SIS
- Exploring technical options (software, hosting) for sustainable operation.
- Identifying capacity gaps and training needs
- Identifying stakeholders and use cases
- Identifying ways for developing a financially sustainable SIS
- Identifying key partners that need to be involved in the development of a full-scale SIS
- Agreeing on next steps for the development of the SIS

This document gathers the information collected and validated during the workshop and discussed plan for implementing Soils4Liberia project that details the steps required to achieve a specific goal. In this instance, the goal is a sustainable national SIS in Liberia that will last beyond the initial phases of project funding, be built on best practices, and continue to meet the needs of users.

Workshop Day 1:

The workshop commenced with welcome remarks from the director of division of Land development and water resources, department of technical services at Ministry of Agriculture MoA, CARI, ISRIC, and IITA. This was followed by an introduction of participants and an overview of the program and its expected outputs by IITA.

Session 1 – Benefits of using the SIS framework

Betony Colman from ISRIC presented the SIS framework, a brief explanation on what is FAIR data, the FAIR process framework, and why is FAIR good for soil data projects. This followed by a Q&A session with the participants.

Session 2 – Current state of LibSIS and Live demo

Mr. Halala Willie Kokulo and the technical representative in CARI, Mr. Harris Yanquoi presented the current state of LibSIS and a live demo of the current platform from FAO pilot project:

- A pilot project led by FAO was implemented in one selected county, serving as a proof of concept for a Soil Information System (SIS). The pilot data is currently maintained and owned by FAO (<https://www.fao.org/global-soil-partnership/resources/highlights/detail/en/c/1648350/>)
- The goal is to establish a fully owned and maintained national SIS for Liberia.
- The envisioned system should include a centralized database and an interactive map viewer.
- Main challenges in the current LibSIS:
 1. Soil survey on a national scale is not covered in LibSIS.
 2. Technical capacity in SIS and digital soil mapping are critically limited.
 3. A plan to effectively engage stakeholders and mobilize additional funding to support the SIS in the long term is missing.
 4. Capacity building on Digital Soil Mapping (DSM) and lab upgrade were not included in LibSIS.
 5. Standardized data collection protocols and related trainings are also missing in LibSIS.
- Main objectives for the new LiNSIS in the future are:
 1. Development of a robust sampling design to generate primary data (new field campaign).
 2. Addressing key thematic areas such as:
 - a. Sustainable crop production
 - b. Climate resilience

- c. Land degradation
- d. Pollution reduction
3. Supporting land use planning and sustainable development goals.
4. Advancing the digitalization of soil data.
5. Establishing an effective data management system.

Session 3 – Ideal System Design

Chrow Khurshid from ISRIC-World Soil Information presented the Soil information Workflow (SIWF). The objectives of this session were to brainstorm the ideal system design-based pilot and determine the key functionalities. The questions below were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- What specific functionalities or features (e.g. dashboards, maps, data security, mobile accessibility, offline access) is missing from the current SIS?
- What are you expecting the SIS will serve you?
- What are the technical and digital literacy gaps (among users)?

Two groups, each consisting of 7 to 9 participants, were formed to discuss the topic using the questions provided. A summary of the group discussions is outlined below:

- The current LibSIS platform is managed by FAO. On a national level in Liberia no system is available, several essential features are wanted, including:
 1. Dashboard
 2. Mobile accessibility
 3. Data security
 4. Geo-referenced points
 5. National Data (including the other 14 counties)
 6. Offline Accessibility
 7. Other Crops – rice & palm, site specific
 8. User/Farmer friendly
 9. Location labels (villages/counties)
 10. Visual aids – if too acidic what will a specific crop look like?
 11. Soil Archiving
- The new LiNSIS is desired to fulfil multiple roles, including:
 1. Fertilizer formulation and site specific geo-referencing.
 2. Updated soil data and soil information repository.
 3. Mobile app for farmers (crop specific info) and User friendly platform for data serving to ensure broader accessibility and usability.
 4. AI functionality, voice command in local languages.
 5. Spatial data and modelling and downloadable data in pdf, excel, arc-gis format.
- Additionally the technical and digital literacy gaps are:
 1. Need for lab data interpretation

2. Digital knowledge on soil inventory
3. Awareness on the SIS user
4. Human Capacities
5. Access to smart phones
6. Infrastructure gaps – even if it is online can the farmers actually access it?

Session 4 – SIS stakeholder map and requirements

The objective of this session was to identify the user requirements and use cases beyond fertility maps, soil degradation monitoring, and others. The questions below were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- Who are potential users and data producers?
- What decisions do potential users need to take that require (or would benefit from) soil data?
- Define SIS requirements to address the needs; why would they use a SIS?
- What are the use cases?

Two groups, each consisting of 7 to 9 participants, were formed to discuss the topic.

Key outcomes from group discussions:

- Potential users and data producers of LiNSIS:
 - **Potential Data Users:**
 1. SHFs/Cooperatives
 2. NGOs
 3. CARI
 4. Local communities
 5. Local authorities
 6. MACs
 7. Land use planners
 8. Farmers/cooperatives
 9. Extensionists
 10. Agronomists
 11. Land authorities
 12. Environmentalists
 13. Policy makers
 14. Investors
 15. Researchers

- **Potential Data Producers:**
 1. MOA, CARI, LISGIS, Tertiary Institutions, Local farmers, NGOs, Development Partners, EPA, FDA
 2. International partners- EU, IITA, WB, ISRIC, FAO
 3. Research/ Academic institutions- CARI, UL, Cuttington Academic, Stella Maris University

- **Why would the users need to use a SIS?**

Making informed decisions, fertiliser, nutrient management, maximise yield, increase productivity, investment,

- **What decision can they make?**
 1. Fertilizer and pesticide recommendations
 2. Soil health
 3. Agronomic Practices
 4. Land Suitability
 5. Agronomic Practice
 6. Drafting National soil use related practices
 7. Right crop/right soil
 8. Make sound decision on the 4 r's stewardship
 9. Soil type needs

- **What are the SIS requirements?**
 1. User friendly
 2. Data Visualisation
 3. Data synchronisation
 4. Offline access
 5. Data quality and reporting tools
 6. GIS (spatial data)

- **Why would they use a SIS?**
 1. Sound decision making
 2. Contextualise tools
 3. Improve crop production
 4. Sustainable land management
 5. Data security and ethical compliance
 6. Support research and innovation
 7. Efficient and time saving

- **Use Cases:**
 1. Site specific fertiliser recommendations
 2. Land suitability analysis
 3. Remote Sensing
 4. Soil health management
 5. Precision Agriculture
 6. Risk analysis and monitoring soil degradation
 7. Data access
 8. Climate Change

Session 5 – Data requirements

The objective of this session was to identify the data challenges. Below questions were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- How should user permissions and data access be managed?
- What are the data challenges?
- What are the data requirements from user perspective?
- What data policies, strategies and mandates exist?
- How can data sharing be achieved between SIS related efforts?
- How can the FAIR data principles strengthen the SIS?

Summary of group discussions:

Each of the two groups (7-9 participants per group) used guiding questions to explore the topic. Key advice from all group discussions are summarized below:

- **How should user permissions and data access be managed?**
 - Role based Access control
 1. System administrator – user management
 2. Data manager - upload, edit, improve, delete
 3. Researcher+/Consultants – view and download data (+ only within Liberia)
 4. Farmers/ community users – viewing rights
 5. Gvnt planners – view and download data
 - Data access request and approval workflow
 1. Submit request
 2. Temporary access
 3. Farmers should not pay for viewing data
 4. Open access on a national level only, payment applies for non-Liberian users.
 - User system Administration
 1. User identification/categoristaion – based on data they need from the system
 2. Type of access
 3. Access time (length and duration)
 - Access code (paid)
 1. Issue of code for different users
 2. Purpose specific (farming, policy making, research)
- **What are the data challenges?**
 - Inadequate awareness
 - Limited / lack of data

- Poor infrastructure
 - Low capacity of users
 - Lack of data experts (managers)
 - Limited awareness of data that is available
 - Weak sustainability plans
- **What are the data requirements from user perspective?**
 - Original clean data (standardized)
 - Available updated data (soil crop specific)
 - Multiple data storage and format (backup)
 - Accessible data repository
 - Metadata, eg: data generation, data validation, data management
 - Profile data in different formats
 - Time series
 - Soil physical and chemical properties
 - Decision support tools
 - Risk maps
 - Reports
 - **What data policies, strategies and mandates exist?**
 - Liberia national data sharing and exchange policy (exists, for all data)
 - Limited policies on data sharing access and management
 - Not aware of a mandate – if it exists at all
 - **How can data sharing be achieved between SIS related efforts?**
 - Integrate with centralised data platform
 - Application program API
 - Drafting of national policies for data sharing in SIS
 - National data repository establishment
 - Access to local/international updated data
 - **How can FAIR data principles strengthen the SIS**
 - Make soil maps
 - Lab results + associated field data (erosion presence, land management etc)
 - Fertility data easy to locate through centralised catalogues
 - Prevent data duplication by helping users access existing data sets
 - Increase data updates for real - world use
 - FAIR principles strengthened SIS by data that are – validated, reproducible for decision making
 - Impact: More accessible, more trustworthy, more people will use (and pay) for SIS, long term sustainability, improves management and use of soil resources, improves stakeholder awareness, evidence based

recommendations, improved research policy linkage, improve regional (West Africa) and global data harmonisation.

Workshop Day 2:

Welcoming and reflections from day one was carried on by MoA, CARI, IITA, and ISRIC.

Session 1- Future of the SIS

The objective of this session was to explore future hosting of the SIS and what would be technically and organizationally feasible. Below questions were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- **Future of the SIS - Future Hosting Scenarios**
 - What technical and institutional options exist for relocating or duplicating the SIS?
 - Hosting in a Liberia government institution (e.g., Ministry server)?
 - National research institution or university?
 - Cloud-based hosting (e.g., AWS, Azure, African cloud services)?
- **Future of the SIS - Ownership and Governance**
 - Who should be the long-term technical administrator of the SIS?
 - What capacities are needed for this entity (e.g., IT support, GIS skills, cybersecurity)?
 - How can the technical ownership align with institutional ownership?
 - Which institution in Liberia should be responsible for the long-term technical and financial management of the SIS?

Summary of group discussions:

Each group (7-9 participants) explored the topic using guiding questions. Key insights from all two groups are outlined below:

- **Proposed future hosting, ownership and governance:**
 - There are several Technical Institutions that can host or support hosting the LiNSIS such as LISGIS Liberia Institute of Statistics and Geo Spatial Information System, MOA, CARI and UL. The work can be coordinated via a steering committee. However, they all lack capacities.
 - MoA should be the owner and the host of SIS with the physical structure may be based in CARI . The long term technical ownership will be at Liberia National Soil Information Centre (LiNSIC). A new team that will be set up in this centre, which will have 4 sub units:
 - Data collection unit – field campaign and data collection monitoring and analysis
 - Data center – data processing, tools and apps

- Soil management unit – advisory and land management, application of use cases
- Training unit - oversee and coordinate capacity building efforts
- Alignment of technical ownership with institutional ownership by MOA and LiNSIC: there is no steering committee needed. MoA will appoint seconded staff from other institutions, LiNSIC will be autonomous in the way it carries out its activities and report to the MOA.
- Soils4Liberia project will hire and train team members, who can then serve as inception staff within institutes. Afterwards, these institutes may hire them directly, enabling them to further train others within the organization.

Session 2- Long term sustainability

The objective of this session was to explore financial strategies to ensure the long-term sustainability of LiNSIS. Below questions were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- **Long term sustainability - Cost Structure – Understanding Financial Needs**
 - What are the key cost categories in the SIS lifecycle (e.g. personnel, tech infrastructure, data management, capacity building)?
 - What is the estimated cost for the next 1–3 years across the next development phases that the SIS will need to go through (initiation, design, implementation)
 - Which costs are already covered (e.g. by the government, OCP Foundation) and which are still unfunded?
- **Long term sustainability - Blending Core and Value-Added Financing**
 - What government budget lines could potentially support the SIS (e.g. agriculture, digital infrastructure, environment)?
 - Could a dedicated SIS funding unit or fundraising mechanism (e.g. grant writing team, PPP unit) be established?
- **Long term sustainability - Revenue Streams and Public-Private Collaboration**
 - What services or information could the SIS tailor for private sector clients (e.g. fertilizer companies, agribusinesses)?
 - What types of users (e.g. extension agents, local governments, NGOs) would be willing to pay for enhanced, user-specific data?
 - Are there existing consulting, training, or soil analysis services that SIS could build upon to generate income?

Summary of group discussions:

Two groups (each with 7-9 participants) discussed the financial and funding aspects of LiNSIS. The key findings are summarized below:

- Key cost categories in the LiNSIS lifecycle:
 - Personal cost
 - Data collection
 - Data management
 - Technical infrastructure – lab, computer, back-up system, server
 - Capacity building
 - Web development
 - Internet services
 - Logistics
 - Housing for the center
 - Communication
 - Utility (water, electric)
 - Initiation phase, Design, and Information, will be covered financially by Soils4Liberia project.
- Funding could potentially be allocated from the Ministry of Agriculture (MoA)
- Proposed financial mechanisms and structures:
 - Establish a dedicated SIS funding unit to manage financial sustainability with in LiNSIC .
 - Generate income from international users and fertilizer companies.
 - Secure core funding contributions from MoA' budgets
 - Potential fundraising mechanisms in future, once the SIS is fully functioning:
 - Apply user fees for premium services and consultancy using SIS resources
 - Charge access fees for specific data sets
 - Introduce platform access fees for certain types of users
- Public-Private collaboration opportunities:
 - Partner with fertilizer companies to support and improve fertilizer formulation using SIS data.
 - Collaborate with agro-industry companies for applied use of soil and crop data.
 - Engage with farmers' organizations, extension agencies, and international NGOs for:
 - Soil sample analysis through UL laboratories/ LiNSIC centre
 - Service-based income generation for LiNSIS
 - Offer consultancy services related to:
 - Soil and crop data interpretation

- Fertilizer recommendations
- Decision support systems

Session 3- Partnership model

Below questions were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- Who are the critical partners needed to successfully implement and maintain the SIS in Liberia?
- What roles should each stakeholder group play in the SIS ecosystem?
- What institutional arrangement or coordination mechanism is needed to govern the partnership?
- How can we ensure that the partnership is inclusive, transparent, and responsive to stakeholder needs over time?
- What agreements or commitments (e.g. MoUs, data-sharing protocols) are needed to formalize the collaboration?

In a panel discussion, the participants identified critical partners and their roles in LiNSIS as below:

- **MoA** – Administration, financial support, and owner
- **CARI** – Produce data and ensure data quality
- **UL** – Produce data, lab analysis and support capacity building in data analysis
- **Cuttington University** – Produce data
- **Tubman University** – Produce data
- **Private sector** – Users and contributors of data
- **LISGIS** – Ensure data quality and support GIS integration
- **NGOs (FAO, INGOs, WB, IFAD)** – Produce and use data, particularly in farmer value chains
- **LLA (Liberia Land Authority)** – Data users; involved in demarcating agricultural land (including potential agricultural land) and providing related information
- **EPA (Environmental Protection Agency):**
 1. Use data to inform regulations and policies
 2. Focus on climate change, resource mobilization, and environmental monitoring (soil erosion, deforestation)
 3. Potential budget contributor and data provider
 4. Draft environmental policies
- **FDA (Forest Development Agency):**
 1. Use soil data to guide conservation activities and land management practices

2. Provide data on forest land
 3. Contribute to fertilizer and farming practice management (e.g., deforestation, shifting cultivation)
 4. Develop policies on forest resources
- **LLA, EPA, FDA** – Key stakeholders for support; alignment and further discussions needed to ensure readiness.
 - **International partnerships:**
 1. FAO - previously development of SIS
 2. IITA - technical capacity
 3. ISRIC - strategic guidance
 4. EU
 5. IFAD
 6. World Bank
 7. AfDB
 - **Additional users identified:**
 1. Bureau of National Concessions – Data users; oversee processes before investments move to higher levels (met during scoping)
 2. Farmer Cooperatives / Cooperative Development Agency – Build farmer capacity and collect data
 - **What institutional arrangement or coordination mechanism is needed to govern the partnership?**
 1. Raise stakeholders awareness
 2. Maintain semi-autonomous status – without too much influence from the ministry
 3. Partnership strategy – at what level is who coming in where
 4. PPP framework
 - **How can we ensure that the partnership is inclusive, transparent and responsive to stakeholder needs over time?**
 1. Steering committee with members from SIS stakeholders – with clear roles defined, with a representative from each partner, meeting at least twice a year, with higher frequency (quarterly) in the initiation phase.
 2. legal bindings – PPA framework/MoU/data sharing agreement

Session 4- Next steps

Below questions were used to identify the next steps for LiNSIS with the stakeholders' groups:

- What are the immediate action items based on the discussions in the previous sessions?
- Which short-term priorities should be addressed first, and what is the timeline for each?
- Who will be responsible for each key action, and how can accountability be ensured?

The actions are provided in the table below.

Table 1 Action points

Action point	Account-able (the institution "responsible" reports to)	Respon-sible (assigned to carry out the task)	Support	Timeline	Priority level 1=high 2=medium 3=low
Inception Meeting	IITA	IITA	All + third parties	Aug 2025	1
Technical discussion and consultations > sampling design	IITA ISRIC	IITA ISRIC CARI	MoA , UL	August-Sept 2025	1
Launch/Kick Off	IITA	ALL	ALL	Oct 2025	1
Soil sampling and lab Protocol development	IITA	IITA	MoA, CARI, UL	Sept-Nov 2025	2

Training & capacity building on soil sampling, lab analysis, DSM, and data management	IITA ISRIC WA HUB	IITA ISRIC WA HUB	MATE	Oct 2025- Oct 27	2
Lab upgrade	IITA	UL	WA HUB	Sept 2025- Jan 2026	
Field campaign	IITA	IITA CARI	MATE UL MoA Stella Marris Polytechnic University Whoever has capacity	Jan-Sept 2026	
Soil analysis	IITA	UL	IITA	Mar-Dec 2026	
Lab quality control	IITA	IITA	UL	Mar-Dec 2026	
System design – technical architecture	ISRIC	ISRIC	IITA WAHUB LISGIS	Sept 2025 – Mar 2026	
Mapping and image interpretation	ISRIC	ISRIC	IITA WAHUB	Jan 2027	3
Steering committee meeting	IITA	ALL	ALL	Oct 2025	2

Scientific and technical advisory group meeting	IITA	ALL	ALL	Oct 2025	2
---	------	-----	-----	----------	---

Annex 1: Workshop Program

Day 1

Breakfast and registration | 08:00 - 09:30

Session 1: setting the scene | 09:30 -10:00

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
3'	Welcome by Moderator Samuel Mesele	Goals and format for the workshop <i>The moderator will introduce each speaker before they speak</i>
10'	Ministry of Agriculture/ CARI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome remarks The needs for a SIS in Liberia The motivation of the government to develop and own a fully functioning SIS
5'	University of Liberia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The need for understanding best practice in the development of soil information systems
5'	FAO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drivers for having supported the development of a SIS pilot in Liberia Main outcomes of the Pilot Project
5'	IITA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation of the West Africa Hubs project Goals for the workshop and how it fits with the project activities and goals
2'	Moderator Samuel Mesele	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Key takeaways from initial presentations

Session 2: Introduction to the SIS framework | 10:00 - 10:30

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
3'	Moderator Harris Yanquoi	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction, objectives and format of the session
20'	Betony Colman ISRIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction to the Framework for Sustainable National Soil Information Systems (SIS Framework) Value of FAIR data principles for SISs
5'	Q&A from the audience Moderator Harris Yanquoi	

Group photo and coffee break | 10:30-11:00

Session 3: Current status of SIS and live demo pilot SIS | 11:00 – 12:00

Objective: To present the current capabilities and limitations of the existing pilot SIS.

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
2'	Moderator Harris Yanquoi	Session Introduction
5'	Ministry of Agriculture / CARI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current state of soil information pilot in Liberia • Plans and goals for LibSIS in the long term
35'	FAO	Live walkthrough of pilot SIS (platform or mockup) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the lessons learned? • What are the current functionalities in the SIS? • What use cases does it serve? • What do you want to keep in the future SIS?
20'	Q&A from the audience Moderator	
3'	Moderator Harris Yanquoi	Key takeaways and preparation for action planning

Session 4: Ideal system design | 12:00 – 13:00

Objective: To understand the requirements and expectations of Liberia SIS users to inform the design of technically feasible, user-friendly, and scalable architecture that is FAIR data compliant.

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
5'	Moderator Harris Yanquoi	Session Introduction
10'	Dr. Chow Khurshid ISRIC	Soil Information Workflow: possible elements of a SIS
45'	Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What specific functionalities or features (e.g. dashboards, maps, data security, mobile accessibility, offline access) is missing from the current SIS? • What are you expecting the SIS will serve you? • What are the technical and digital literacy gaps (among users)?

Networking lunch | 13:00-14:00

Session 5: SIS stakeholder map and requirements | 14:00 – 15:00

Objective: To identify the user requirements and use cases beyond fertility maps, soil degradation monitoring, and others

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
--------	---------	-----------------------------

2'	Moderator Harris Yanquoi	Session Introduction
55'	Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify potential users and (data) producers; Collect users' needs; what decisions do potential users need to take that require (or would benefit from) soil data? Define SIS requirements to address the needs; why would you/ they use a SIS? What are the use cases?
3'	Moderator Harris Yanquoi	Key takeaways and preparation for action planning

Session 6: Data requirements | 15:00 – 16:00
Objective: to identify the data challenges

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
2'	Moderator	Session Introduction
55'	Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How should user permissions and data access be managed? What are the data challenges? What are the data requirements from user perspective? What data policies, strategies and mandates exist? How can data sharing be achieved between SIS related efforts? How can the FAIR data principles strengthen the SIS?
3'	Moderator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Key takeaways

Close of day 1 | 16:00 – 16:30

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
2'	Moderator	
5'	MoA / CARI	Key takeaways from day 1
5'	University of Liberia	
5'	IITA	
3'	Moderator	Official closure of day 1

Annex 2: Flipcharts from different groups

Data requirements
GROUP B - ①

- Users Permission & Access Management**
 - User System Administration**
 - User Identification/Categorization
 - Types of access
 - Access Time (Length of access & duration)
 - Access Code**
 - Issue different code to different users
 - Purpose specific user (farming, research & policy making)
- Data Challenges**
 - Limited data
 - Low/Lack of data Experts (scientists or clerks)
 - Limited awareness on data availability
 - Limited digital/data Infrastructure (network, Internet)
- Data Requirement - Users**
 - Available updated data (soil-crop specific)
 - Accessible data/repository
 - Multiple data storage and formats
 - Meta data: ex: data generation, data validation and data management.
- Data policies/Strategies/Mandates**
 - Policies**
 - Limited policies on data sharing, access management
 - Strategies**
 - LIBSIS/FAO
 - SOIL/Liberia
 - Mandates**
 - May not be available
- Data Sharing thru. SIS Efforts**
 - Drafting National policies for data sharing in SIS
 - National data repository establishment
 - Access to local/Int'l updated data
- FAIR**
 - FAIR principles strengthen SIS by producing data that are:
 - Validated
 - Reproducible for decision making

Data requirements
GROUP A

- Data Access:**
 - Role based access control
 - System administrator - User Management
 - Data Manager - upload, edit, approve, delete
 - Researcher/consultants - view and download data
 - Farmer/community users - viewing right
 - Government planners - view and download data

*Data access request and approval work flow

 - Submit access request
 - Temporary access
 - Farmers should not pay for data viewing
 - All private organizations/institutions should pay for data
- Data Gap**
 - Inadequate awareness
 - Poor Infrastructure
 - Low capacity of users
 - Weak sustainability plans
- ② GRA / Data requirements**
- ③ Data Requirements**
 - Program (clean data) Standardized
 - Profile data in different formats
 - Time Series
 - Soil physical and chemical properties
 - Mobile apps integration
 - SMS
 - Risk maps
 - Reports
- ④ Policies**
 - Liberia National data sharing and exchange Policy
 - Liberia Soil Information System (LIBSIS)
- ⑤ Data Sharing**
 - Integrate with centralized data platform (LIBSIS)
 - Application program Interface (API)
- ⑥ FAIR**
 - Make soil maps
 - Lab results + Field data
 - Facilitate data easy to locate through a centralized catalogues
 - Prevent data duplication by helping users existing data set
 - Increase data updates for real-world use

↓

 - Improves management and use of soil resources.
 - Increase stakeholder awareness
 - Evidence based recommendations
 - Improved research-policy linkages
 - Improved targeted investment.
 - Improved regional data harmonization (WA-Hub) + Global.

Stakeholders
GROUP B

① Point 1:

<p><u>USERS</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Farmers/Cooperatives * Extensionists * Agronomists * Land Authorities (INAG, INGA) * Stakeholders (Environmentalists) * Policy Makers * Investors * Concessionaires * Researchers 	<p><u>PRODUCERS</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * International Partners EU, FAO, IITA, WFP, IFAD * Research & Academic Institutions CARI, UL, Cotonou Academe * FARMERS SMPU * Government Agencies (MOA, EPA, F.D.A. LG.S etc)
---	---

Stakeholders
Point 2

② (R)

- * Fertilizers & Pesticides Recommendations
- * Soil Health
- * Agronomic Practices (Drought Resistant Crops)
- * Land Sustainability
- * Drafting National soil use related Policies & Investment.

Points:

- * Reliable, Available and Accessible Soil data (NOT management, Maximizing yield, investment, policy making, ...)

Point 4:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Land Degradation * Drought Analysis * Crop Stability Assessment * Land use Management * Data Assessment Services * Precision Agriculture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Risk Assessment * Soil Health Monitoring * Land use Management * Weather
---	---

Stakeholders
GROUP A

① Data producers:

- MOA, CARI, LISGIS, Tertiary Institutions, Local farmers, NGOs, Development Partners, EPA, FDA

Data users:

- SHFs/Cooperatives, NGOs, CARI, Researchers, Investors, Local Communities, local authorities, MACS, Policy makers, private sector actors, Land use Planners, Businesses

② Decisions:

- Crop to be planted based on soil type and fertility
- Amount of fertilizer to be supplied/applied
- Make sound decisions on the CRs Stewards
- Soil type needs

③ Requirements:

- User-friendly
- Data Visualization
- Data Synchronization
- Offline access
- Data quality and reporting tools
- GIS (Spatial data)

Stakeholders
3) Why SIS?

③

- Sound decision making
- Contextualize tool
- Improve agricultural productivity
- Sustainable land Mgt
- Data Security and ethical compliance
- Support research and Innovation
- Efficient and time Saving

④ Use cases:

- Site specific fertilizer recommendations
- Land Stability analysis
- Remote Sensing Integration
- Soil Health Management
- Precision Agriculture
- Risk analysis and Soil degradation
- Data access ^{Monitoring}
- Climate change

DAY 2 GROUPS

Point 1

- * Technical Institutions
 - LISGIS
 - MDA
 - CARI
 - University of Liberia
- * Cloud Services
 - ISTRIC
 - African Cloud Services
 - Microsoft (Azure)
 - Google Cloud platform (GCP)

Point 2

- * Ownership
 - MOA (Through a center for National Soil Data Management CeNSDaM)
- * Governance & Administration
 - LISGIS

Point 3

- * Capacity Needs
 - IT Support, GIS Skills, Cybersecurity, Data Clerk etc.

Point 4

- * Technical & Financial Management
 - MOA

Points

- * Alignment of Technical Ownership with Institutional domain
 - CeNSDaM will be an annex to MOA
 - ↑
 - Establishing

Institutional ownership

Technical ownership

MoA ↔ LISNSIC with 4 sub-units

→ Supports from stakeholders/partners:-

1. CARI - Field
2. UL - Lab
- 3.

→ How Institutional + Technical owners align?

→ Long term

- technical
- financial
- Administrative
- policy

→ Where SIS should be hosted?

LISNSIC Servers in Data Centre

GROUP A

① FUTURE HOSTING SCENARIOS

① Hosting - CARI

② Long-term technical administrator at the SIS - CARI

- Needed capabilities:-
 - ✓ IT Support
 - * Server and network mgmt infrastructure
 - * Database administration
- GIS Skills**
 - * GIS analysis (Arc-GIS, QGIS)
 - * satellite imagery interpretation
- Cyber Security**
 - * Data interpretation and server logging
 - * secured hosting protocol (http)

GROUP A

③ Technical ownership align with Institution

- Through steering committee
- MOA - Chair
- CARI - Secretary
- FDA
- LISGIS
- LLA
- EPA
- Universities
- MME

④ Long-term technical and financial mgmt CARI

Long term sustainability

GROUP B

1. PERSONNEL (data collector, IT specialist, GIS specialist, data clerk, cybersecurity specialist, D.O., DDG, Admin, financial) \$25,000
2. Technical Infrastructure (Data soft, computer, Data server, internet Service, stationaries, furniture, communication)
3. → Data Management / Website Maintenance, cloud
4. Capacity Building
 - Training personnel
 - Data collector
 - Data entry clerk, etc.
5. Funding Models
 - MOA budget line
 - International partners - IFAD / ADB / WB / Global agricultural fund
 - proposal writing (grant)

REVENUE STREAMS

- → NGOs
- → Fertilizer companies

5. Revenue Streams

* Quality and reliable data will attract the Private Sectors, and this strategy will bring ease to various NGOs, Fertilizer Companies.

* Low Scale training & Low Scale Consultancy by the University of Liberia, Soil Lab is being carried out.

Long term funding

GROUP A ①

Cost structure

Ⓐ Key Cost Categories

- Personnel Cost
- Data collection
- Data mgt
- Technical Infrastructure (lab, computer, back-up system, servers, etc)
- capacity building
- web development
- logistics
- Housing for the center
- Communication
- utility (water, electricity)
- Arc GIS, Q-GIS

Ⓑ

Initiation → Design → Implementation

The cost for the first 3 years has been covered by Soil4Liberia

GROUP A ②

c. No Known cost has been covered by the government for the center

d. Funding Models - Potential Gov't budget line

- MOA

e. Dedicated SIS funding unit

- pay for laboratory services
- private sector to pay for data
- Grant proposal writing

f. Revenue streams PPC

- Map Production
- Fertilizer recommendations
- monitor data

What types of users

- Companies
- INGOs, NGOs

GROUP A ③

Existing Consultants

- soil analysis
- Training
- Consultancy
- CARI provides training for small-holder farmers, Corporations, etc

Annex 3: List of Participants

Please be aware photos should only be taken for official communication/social media. Please put a star (*) by your name if you DO NOT wish to be included.

Liberia Soil Information System (SIS) Roadmap Development ATTENDANCE SHEET

Date: _____

FIRST AND NAME	INSTITUTION	POSITION	COUNTY	SEX	PHONE NUMBER	EMAIL ADDRESS	SIGNATURE
Dennis D. Goble	MOA	Soil Tech	Monts	M	0889404031	dennisgoble@moa.gov.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Barthelemy S. Koinoo	MOA	Soil Technician	Monts	F	095591637	barthelemykoinoo@moa.gov.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Sala S. Shon	UL	Director	Monts	M	077667005	sala@ul.edu.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Leony Wege	UL	Dean	Monts	M	088608512	leony@ul.edu.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Oliver R. Tarzo	Stella Maris Polytechnic	Dean	Monts	M	0776697573	oliver@smu.edu.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Nathan K. Zang	MOA	Technical	Monts	M	0777047205	nathan@moa.gov.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Prince Z. Nua	UL	LAB	Monts	M	088608514	prince@ul.edu.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]

Page 1 of 2

Please be aware photos should only be taken for official communication/social media. Please put a star (*) by your name if you DO NOT wish to be included.

Liberia Soil Information System (SIS) Roadmap Development ATTENDANCE SHEET

Date: _____

FIRST AND NAME	INSTITUTION	POSITION	COUNTY	SEX	PHONE NUMBER	EMAIL ADDRESS	SIGNATURE
Sala S. Shon	UL	Director	Monts	M	077667005	sala@ul.edu.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
King Cogle	UL	Dean	Monts	M	0777285801	kingcogle@ul.edu.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Hasan	CARI	Head	Bong	M	0886670274	hasan@carilb.org	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Prince Z. Nua	UL	LAB	Monts	M	088608512	prince@ul.edu.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Quincy S. Nua	MOA	Soil Tech	Bong	M	088668915	quincy@moa.gov.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Samuel Nua	MOA	Soil Tech	Bong	M	088668915	samuel@moa.gov.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Michael	MOA	Soil Tech	Bong	M	088668915	michael@moa.gov.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]

Page 1 of 2

Please be aware photos should only be taken for official communication/social media. Please put a star (*) by your name if you DO NOT wish to be included.

Liberia Soil Information System (SIS) Roadmap Development ATTENDANCE SHEET

Date: _____

FIRST AND NAME	INSTITUTION	POSITION	COUNTY	SEX	PHONE NUMBER	EMAIL ADDRESS	SIGNATURE
Edward Russell	IITA	Assoc. Agronomist	Monts	M	077358924	edward@iita.org	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Joseph A. Koinoo	IITA	Assoc. Agronomist	Monts	M	088647826	joseph@iita.org	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Stella N. Goble	STAR-P	Technical Assistant	Monts	F	088660040	stella@star-p.org	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Prince Z. Nua	CARI	Research Officer	Bong	M	088668915	prince@carilb.org	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Alex D. Koinoo	CARI	Research Officer	Bong	M	088668915	alex@carilb.org	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]

Page 1 of 2

Please be aware photos should only be taken for official communication/social media. Please put a star (*) by your name if you DO NOT wish to be included.

Liberia Soil Information System (SIS) Roadmap Development ATTENDANCE SHEET

Date: _____

FIRST AND NAME	INSTITUTION	POSITION	COUNTY	SEX	PHONE NUMBER	EMAIL ADDRESS	SIGNATURE
Shawn N. Goble	STAR-P	Technical Assistant	Monts	M	088660040	shawn@star-p.org	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
King Cogle	UL	Dean	Monts	M	0777285801	kingcogle@ul.edu.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Jacobs Dennis	MOA	Soil Specialist	Bong	M	088668915	jacobs@moa.gov.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Justin G. Eddy	MOA	Soil Specialist	Monts	M	088668915	justin@moa.gov.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Oliver R. Tarzo	Stella Maris Polytechnic University	Dean	Monts	M	0776697573	oliver@smu.edu.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Nathan K. Zang	MOA	Technical	Monts	M	0777047205	nathan@moa.gov.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]

Page 1 of 2

Please be aware photos should only be taken for official communication/social media. Please put a star (*) by your name if you DO NOT wish to be included.

Liberia Soil Information System (SIS) Roadmap Development ATTENDANCE SHEET

Date: _____

FIRST AND NAME	INSTITUTION	POSITION	COUNTY	SEX	PHONE NUMBER	EMAIL ADDRESS	SIGNATURE
Hilda J. Koinoo	MOA	Director	Monts	M	088668915	hilda@moa.gov.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]

Page 1 of 2

Please be aware photos should only be taken for official communication/social media. Please put a star (*) by your name if you DO NOT wish to be included.

Liberia Soil Information System (SIS) Roadmap Development ATTENDANCE SHEET

Date: _____

FIRST AND NAME	INSTITUTION	POSITION	COUNTY	SEX	PHONE NUMBER	EMAIL ADDRESS	SIGNATURE
Edward Russell	IITA	Assoc. Agronomist	Monts	M	077358924	edward@iita.org	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Joseph A. Koinoo	IITA	Assoc. Agronomist	Monts	M	088647826	joseph@iita.org	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Dennis D. Goble	MOA	Soil Tech	Monts	M	088668915	dennis@moa.gov.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Prince Z. Nua	UL	LAB	Monts	M	088608512	prince@ul.edu.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Prince Z. Nua	CARI	Research Officer	Bong	M	088668915	prince@carilb.org	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
Alex D. Koinoo	CARI	Research Officer	Bong	M	088668915	alex@carilb.org	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]
William S. Nua	MOA	Soil Tech	Monts	M	088668915	william@moa.gov.lr	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> [Signature]

Page 1 of 2

NAME	INSTITUTION	POSITION	COUNTRY	SEX	PHONE NUMBER	EMAIL ADDRESS	SIGNATURE
Julie N. Saha	UL	LAB Technicial	Monr.	F	07868028	julie@ul.edu	[Signature]
Helen Anani	CARI	MOB	Borg	M	0886679274	helen@carilab.com	[Signature]
Joseph S. Kallie	CARI	SOIL Scientist	Borg	M	0886585715	jsk@carilab.com	[Signature]
Sala S. Shool	UL	Director	Mont	M	0886405866	ss@ul.edu	[Signature]
Muhammad S. Kallie	MOA	Soil technician	Mont	F	0775591633 086.374637	muhammad@ul.edu	[Signature]

Page 1 of 2

Please be aware photos/videos will be taken for external communications/social media. Please put a star (*) by your name if you DO NOT wish to be included.

Liberia Soil Information System (SIS) Roadmap Development ATTENDANCE SHEET

Date: _____

FIRST AND NAME	INSTITUTION	POSITION	COUNTRY	SEX	PHONE NUMBER	EMAIL ADDRESS	SIGNATURE
Supriat N. Kromah	ITTA	DATA Scientist	Liberia	M	011-455560	supriat@itita.org	[Signature]
Shera Komare Kromah	ITTA	DATA SPECIALIST	NIGERIA	M	08122057677	skromah@itita.org	[Signature]
Grace E. Mollay	Inger	Rept.	Mont	F	088661503	gracem@itita.org	[Signature]
Mahala Williams Krokulo	MCA	Director	Mahameda	M	0886556358	mahala@itita.org	[Signature]
AUSTIN G. YANNEY	MOA	System Specialist	Mont	M	0886549514	ayanne@itita.org	[Signature]
APOLINA S. CLARENTE	EU	PROGRAMS OFFICER	EU	M	0888904647	apolina@itita.org	[Signature]
Edric David	ELRC	Reporter	Mont	M	0886115813	edric@itita.org	[Signature]

Page 1 of 2

Willie S. Kallie	MOA	Soil Tech	Mont	F	0775591633	willie@ul.edu	[Signature]
Dennis A. Ruel	UNSA	Soil Tech	Mont	M	0881404251	dennis@ul.edu	[Signature]
Daniel M. S. S. S. S.	ITTA	Equipment	Liberia	M	0888875577	daniel@itita.org	[Signature]
Oliver K. Jarzo	ITTA	Dean	Mont	M	0776697572	oliver@itita.org	[Signature]
Muhammad M. Ganyo	ITTA	Accountant	Mont	F	0770215512	muhammad@itita.org	[Signature]
William N. Zany	MOA	Technician	Mont	M	0897047405	william@itita.org	[Signature]

Page 1 of 2